

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN IMPROVING MOTOR ACTIVITY OF CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

Bahriddinova I.X

U.S U.P.E and S teacher of the Department
of Adaptive Physical Education and Parasports

baxruddinovabror@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14393570>

Annotation: This article gives information about how to use physical education tools for treating children with cerebral palsy and how important physical exercises are in increasing their movement activity is explained.

Key words: Cerebral palsy, physical therapy, intellectual disability, coordination, balance, strength, flexibility.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bolalar serebral falajligi kasaligiga chalingan bolalarni faollashtirishda davolovchi jismoniy tarbiya vositalaridan foydalanish uslubiyati hamda jismoniy mashiqning bolalar hayotidagi o'rnini haqida ma'lumot berilgan

Kalit so'zlar: Serebral falajlik, davolovchi jismoniy tarbiya, koordinatsiya, muvozanat, diskinetik.

Introduction. Cerebral palsy (CP) is one of the most common developmental disabilities. CP is the term given for a set of neurological disorders characterised by movement and posture disorders causing activity limitation due to a static disturbance in the developing brain. This is often accompanied by associated impairments and secondary health conditions. CP is not a single pathological entity and described disorders in various motor functions including but not limited to body movement, muscle control, muscle coordination, muscle tone, reflex, fine motor skills, gross motor skills, oral motor functioning, posture, and balance.

What it is: Cerebral palsy (CP) is a group of disorders that affect a person's ability to move and maintain balance and posture. *Cerebral* means having to do with the brain. *Palsy* means weakness in or problems with using the muscles. CP is caused by abnormal brain development or damage to the developing brain that affects a person's ability to control their muscles. CP is the most common motor disability in childhood.

All people with CP have problems with movement and posture. Many also have related conditions such as the following:

- Intellectual disability
- Seizures
- Problems with vision, hearing, or speech
- Changes in the spine (such as scoliosis A)
- Joint problems (such as contractures B)
- Types: Doctors classify CP according to the main type of movement disorder involved. Depending on which areas of the brain are affected, one or more of the following movement disorders can occur:
 - Stiff muscles (spasticity)
 - Uncontrollable movements (dyskinesia)
 - Poor balance and coordination (ataxia)

There are four main types of CP.

▪ **Spastic cerebral palsy.** The most common type of CP is spastic CP. Spastic CP affects about 80% of people with CP. People with spastic CP have increased muscle tone. This

means their muscles are stiff and, as a result, their movements can be awkward. Spastic CP usually is described by which parts of the body are affected:

- **Dyskinetic cerebral palsy.** People with dyskinetic CP have problems controlling the movement of their hands, arms, feet, and legs, making it difficult to sit and walk. Dyskinetic CP includes athetoid, choreoathetoid, and dystonic cerebral palsies. The movements are uncontrollable and can be slow and writhing or rapid and jerky. Sometimes the face and tongue are affected, and the person has a hard time sucking, swallowing, and talking. A person with dyskinetic CP has muscle tone that can change (varying from too tight to too loose) not only from day to day, but even during a single day.

- **Ataxic cerebral palsy.** People with ataxic CP have problems with balance and coordination. They might be unsteady when they walk. They might have a hard time with quick movements or movements that need a lot of control, like writing. They might have a hard time controlling their hands or arms when they reach for something.

- **Mixed cerebral palsy.** Some people have symptoms of more than one type of CP. The most common type of mixed CP is spastic-dyskinetic CP

How does physical therapy help?

Physical therapy is often the first step in treating CP. It can help improve motor skills and can prevent movement problems from getting worse over time. Physical therapy implements strength and flexibility exercises, heat treatment, massages and special equipment to give children with cerebral palsy more independence. The extent to which physical therapy helps depends on the severity and type of each case of cerebral palsy. Children with milder cases of CP may only require some physical therapy to treat their condition. In more severe cases, it may be used alongside other treatments or medications. Beginning physical therapy as early as possible usually gives children the best chances at improvement.

Benefits of physical therapy for cerebral palsy

There are many benefits of physical therapy, from improving mobility to preventing future issues such as contractures and joint dislocations by keeping the body strong and flexible. Many children with CP increase their level of self-reliance through physical therapy. The main goal of physical therapy is to make everyday movements easier for children with cerebral palsy.

Physical therapy can improve:

- Coordination
- Balance
- Strength
- Flexibility
- Endurance
- Pain management
- Posture
- Gait
- Overall health.

Some of the benefits by cerebral palsy type include:

Spastic: Physical therapy can reduce the muscle tension and jerky movements associated with spastic cerebral palsy. Exercises such as stretching can even relieve stiffness over time.

Athetoid - People with athetoid cerebral palsy use physical therapy to increase muscle tone and gain more control over their movements.

Ataxic - There are exercises that can improve balance problems faced by those with ataxic cerebral palsy.

Physical therapists also tailor treatment based on the location of movement issues. Movement issues in children with cerebral palsy can be limited to one half of the body (hemiplegia), the legs (diplegia) or in the torso and all four limbs (quadriplegia). Therapists prescribe special exercises and routines for hemiplegia, diplegia, and quadriplegia that may help the child regain movement in the affected area over time

Conclusion: In conclusion, it is appropriate to say that in order to increase the physical activity of children with cerebral palsy, their type of disease must first be clearly diagnosed by medical personnel. In addition, the selection of physical exercises according to the type and degree of their disease is one of the most important factors.

Used literature

1. Hoshimovich G. S., Duszhanov B. M., Abdumavlanovich t. U. Improvement of the training process of flight and athletes in the initial training group of youth // *asia pacific journal of marketing & management review issn: 2319-2836 impact factor: 8.071. - 2022. - t. 11. – no. 12. - s. 163-176.*
2. G'ofurov Sh. Adaptive physical education of young people with spine injuries using a wheelchair // *mejdunarodnaya nauchno-practicheskaya online conference. - 2021. - t. 4. – s. 24.*
3. Gafurov Sh. X. Bahadir Khoshimovich G'furov Development of movement activity of visually impaired people by popularizing 5x5 football sport in Uzbekistan // *Scientific progress. - 2022. - T. 6.*
4. Valieva N. Yu. Adaptivnaya physical culture as a teaching discipline and social practical area // *Scientific progress. - 2022. - T. 3. – no. – S. 649-655.*
Davlatova L. T. The significance of educational pedagogics in the system of inclusive education and the effectiveness of using interactive technologies in forming the educational environment // *Scientific progress. - 2021. - T. 1. – no. 6. - S. 30-35.*
5. Davlatova L. T. Effectiveness of special exercises for the development of their physical qualities in teaching disabled students to para-volleyball // *fan-sportga. – 2023. – no. 3. - s. 75-77.*
6. Koshbakhtiev I. A., Dadabaev O. J., Ibragimov B. B. Effektivnost optimizatsii planirovaniya podgotovki yunyx sportsmenov po sportivnym edinoborstvam // *actualnye problemy sovershenstvovaniya sistemy nepreryvnogo fizkulturnogo obrazovaniya. - 2020. - s. 236-240.*